

CHEMICAL SCIENCES

THE USE OF FAT-SOLUBLE CO₂-EXTRACTS FROM SPICES WITH HIGH CONTENT OF BIOLOGICALLY ACTIVE SUBSTANCES IN THE FABRICATION OF DRESSINGS

Iushan L.,

*Scientific and Practical Institute of Horticulture,
Viticulture and Food Technologies
Chisinau, Republic of Moldova
Doctor of Technical Sciences
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4028-221X>*

Taran N.,

*Scientific and Practical Institute of Horticulture,
Viticulture and Food Technologies
Chisinau, Republic of Moldova
Ph. Doctor of Technical Sciences
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-1683-0378>*

Karelina M.,

*Scientific and Practical Institute of Horticulture,
Viticulture and Food Technologies
Chisinau, Republic of Moldova
<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8760-9673>*

Terentieva G.,

*Scientific and Practical Institute of Horticulture,
Viticulture and Food Technologies
Chisinau, Republic of Moldova
<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9059-7191>*

Zyryanova E.

*Scientific and Practical Institute of Horticulture,
Viticulture and Food Technologies
Chisinau, Republic of Moldova
<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7625-175X>
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Abstract

The article presents organoleptic characteristics and physicochemical parameters (including lycopene content) in fat-soluble CO₂-extracts from tomato waste with high content of biologically active substances.

As a result, recipes were developed and samples of dressings for salads were produced with the addition of fat-soluble CO₂-extracts from tomato waste. The amount of fat-soluble CO₂-extract from tomato waste in the product is reasoned.

Keywords: tomato waste, fat-soluble CO₂-extracts, biologically active substances, dressings.

Introduction

Currently, several technologies for the fabrication of bioactive components and their use in functional nutrition are known. The world interest in biologically active substances (BAS), which are contained in the raw material characteristic for a certain region, and in food products fortified with BAS has increased significantly in the last 10-15 years.

During the last years, through state and international programs, scientists from countries such as France, Germany, Switzerland, the USA have contributed considerably to the development of a new class of food, pharmaceutical and cosmetic products with biologically active substances, namely CO₂-extracts from raw materials of plant origin.

CO₂-extracts from plant raw materials can be used for the purpose of enriching food products with SBA, fat-soluble vitamins, natural antioxidants, natural taste

and flavors and other complexes that are missing in refined products.

Fat-soluble CO₂-extract from tomato waste obtained in the process of supercritical extraction from the secondary raw material of plant origin, contains biologically active substances (BAS), such as fat-soluble vitamins: carotenoids, including lycopene; tocopherols; polyphenolic substances and polyunsaturated fatty acids.

A possibility of perspective use of fat-soluble CO₂-extract from tomato waste is in the preparation of dressings for salads or other culinary products (snacks, appetizers) in which vegetable oil is included, this fact directing to the expansion of the assortment of traditional products.

Salad dressing sauces are a slightly acidic combination of vegetable oil and water, seasoned and spiced, which have been used to increase the attraction to a

product by improving the taste of fresh or prepared vegetables, fruits, meat, fish, cheeses, eggs and various combinations of them. In certain food cultures, salads with dressing are an important part of menus [1].

Dressings (oil-in-water emulsions), such as mayonnaise and salad sauces, are an important segment of the salad dressings market, which enjoys wide use [1].

Dressings can be prepared before the time of use, but most often they are manufactured as finished products for retail, catering enterprises and other food directions. A growing use is for the production of chilled salads, for restaurants and fast food establishments [1].

Materials and methods

Research will be focused on:

- production in laboratory conditions of fat-soluble CO₂- extracts from tomato waste with high content of biologically active substances;

- determination of organoleptic and physicochemical parameters of fat-soluble CO₂- extracts from tomato waste;

- elaboration of recipes and production in laboratory conditions of dressings fortified with CO₂ - extract from tomato waste with high content of biologically active substances;

- determination of organoleptic, physicochemical and microbiological parameters of dressing fortified with fat-soluble CO₂- extracts from tomato waste.

Determination of organoleptic and physicochemical parameters of fat-soluble CO₂- extracts from tomato waste with high content of biologically active substances were carried out according to the current regulatory documentation:

- Method of determining the acidity index, according to GOST 5476-80;

- Method for determining the peroxide index, according to GOST 26593-85;

- Lycopene content was determined at the spectrophotometer model Spekol 1500 Analytik Jena (Food Quality Control laboratory, IP ISPHTA).

Lycopene from CO₂-extracts from tomato waste was extracted using the mixture of hexane: ethanol:acetone (2:1:1) (v/v). The absorbance was measured at 502 nm, as a reference substance (ethanol, standard) using hexane.

The determination of the organoleptic and physicochemical parameters of the dressings fortified with CO₂-extract from tomato waste with high content of biologically active substances were carried out according to the current regulatory documentation:

- Method for determining soluble dry substances, according to GOST 28562-90;

- Method of determination of titrable acids, according to Ms SR EN 12147-2002;

- Method for determining titrable acids, according to GOST 26188-84.

Results and discussion

The industrial tomato waste (JSC "Orhei-Vit") was used for the research, which was dried, shredded and mixed.

At the installation for CO₂-supercritical extraction, model HA 120-50-01, five samples of fat-soluble CO₂- extracts from tomato waste with high content of biologically active substances were obtained at 5 supercritical extraction regimes (Table 1).

Table 1.

Regimes of CO₂ supercritical extraction from tomato waste

The name of the parameters		Number of extraction regime				
		I	II	III	IV	V
Extractor	Temperature, °C	60	57,9	60	63,5	39,6
	Pressure, MPa	30	30,7	30	30	32,1
	Time, min	90	75	75	75	120
	CO ₂ flow, l/h	45-58	34,1	37	38	35
Separator I	Temperature, °C	70	69,5	70	54,9	49,9
	Pressure, MPa	10,9-11,2	10,3	11	10,6	11,7
Separator II	Temperature, °C	30	30,2	30	31,2	31,3
	Pressure, MPa	5,3-5,6	5,1	5,0	5,6	5,1

Pic. 1. Samples of fat-soluble CO₂-extracts from tomato waste, Separator I and II

The organoleptic parameters of the fat-soluble CO₂-extract from tomato waste are presented in table 2.

Table 2

The organoleptic parameters of the fat-soluble CO₂-extract from tomato waste

No.	Organoleptic parameter	Characteristics
1	External appearance and consistency	Fat-soluble liquid or oily mass with a homogeneous consistency, from fluid to buttery, with or without waxy substances, without other impurities. Stored in the cold, it shows an uneven distribution of waxes in the volume of the product, which disappear easily after mixing
2	Transparency	Translucent
3	Color	Natural color, characteristic of tomatoes, from light red-orange to a dark brick shade
4	Flavor and taste	Pleasant flavor, characteristic of tomatoes; pleasant, strongly pronounced taste of tomato. Taste remanent weak bitter.

The fat-soluble CO₂-extract from tomato waste has a very viscous consistency, which would make it difficult to use it in the food industry. For a more fluid consistency, it is necessary to heat the CO₂-extract from tomato waste.

The physicochemical parameters of fat-soluble CO₂-extracts from tomato waste from Separator I were determined and are presented in table 3.

Table 3

The physicochemical parameters of fat-soluble CO₂-extracts from tomato waste

The name of the parameters	Number of sample				
	I	II	III	IV	V
Acidity index, mg NaOH/g	-	11,35	10,68	9,78	7,61
Peroxide index , mmol O ₂ activ/kg	-	18,15	17,80	16,97	12,58
Lycopene content, mg/100 g	82,32	92,52	95,06	55,58	76,77
	77,95	86,06	93,28	51,69	47,87

The weight of fat-soluble CO₂-extracts from tomato waste obtained in separator I varied from 20.0 to 26.4 g. The weight data of fat-soluble CO₂-extracts from tomato waste specific to each supercritical extraction are indicated in picture 2.

Pic. 2. Weight of fat-soluble CO₂-extracts from tomato waste

The highest amount of fat-soluble CO₂- extract from industrial tomato waste (26,4 g) was obtained at the extraction regime at temperature 60,0 °C in separator I, although the extraction duration 75 min. (sample 3).

It has been established that the concentration of lycopene in fat – soluble CO₂- extracts from tomato waste ranges from 55.58 mg/100 g to 95.06 mg/100 g. For extracts from separator II the lycopene content is within the limits of 47.84-93.28 mg/100 g.

The lycopene content specific to each supercritical extraction are shown in picture 3.

Pic. 3. The lycopene content of fat-soluble CO₂-extracts from tomato waste

The highest amount of of lycopene in fat-soluble CO₂-extract from industrial tomato waste (95.06 mg/100 g) was obtained at the extraction regime at temperature 60,0 °C in separator I, although the extraction duration 75 min. (sample 3).

The content of bioactive compounds in fat-soluble CO₂-extracts of tomato waste was taken into account when developing salad dressing recipes and sample 3 was selected.

To ensure the supply of vitamins in significant quantities, it is advisable to provide a minimum of 15%

of the recommended daily dose, according to HG no. 196 of 25.03.2011 Health Regulation on nutrition and health claims on food products [2].

The recommended daily dose (RDA) for vitamins is established in Government Decision No. 538 of 02.09.2009 Health regulation regarding food supplements, point 15 [3]. As for carotenoids, namely lycopene, the RDA is specified in the Methodical Recommendations "Rational Food" MR 2.3.1.19150-04 [4], and Scientific Opinion on the substantiation of health claims related to lycopene [5] and is 5 mg.

Table 4.

Recommended daily dose (RDA) and quantity in CO₂-extracts

Name of vitamins	Recommended daily dose, mg	Maximum daily dose, mg	15% of RDA, mg
Carotenoids	15,0	30,0	2,25
Lycopene	5,0	10,0	0,75
Vitamin E	10,0	30,0	1,5

5 basic recipes were developed for the preparation of salad dressings, which were varied by introducing CO₂-extract from tomato waste, as an ingredient - source of biologically active substances.

To fortify the product with lycopene we must add 0.8 mg fat-soluble CO₂- extract from tomato waste per 100 g of product.

Table 5.

Recipes of salad dressings with and without added fat-soluble CO₂- extract

No.	The name of product	Salad dressings with addition of				
		Apple vinegar	Grape vinegar	Balsamic vinegar	Apple acidifier	Grape acidifier
1	Vegetable oil	35,0-34,2	35,0-34,2	35,0-34,2	35,0-34,2	35,0-34,2
2	CO ₂ -extract	0,0-0,8	0,0-0,8	0,0-0,8	0,0-0,8	0,0-0,8
3	Apple puree (SU 16 %)	22,0	22,0	22,0	22,0	22,0
4	Acidifier / Vinegar	5,0	5,0	5,0	12,0	20,0
5	Sugar	6,0	6,0	6,0	5,0	3,0
6	Salt	2,0	2,0	2,0	2,0	2,0
7	Pectin	0,5	0,5	0,5	0,5	0,5
8	Spices	1,0	1,0	1,0	1,0	1,0
9	Water	Rest	Rest	Rest	Rest	Rest
	Total	100	100	100	100	100

For all assortment of the salad dressings, the base was vegetable oil and apple puree, and as an acidifier was used: apple vinegar, grape vinegar, balsamic vinegar, natural apple acidifier, natural grape acidifier. For the assortment of salad dressings with the addition of fat-soluble CO₂-extract from tomato waste part of the vegetable oil was replaced with extract.

Pic. 4. Samples of salad dressings

Salad dressing is prepared according to the technology in several stages.

In the first stage, sunflower vegetable oil is mixed with the fat-soluble CO₂-extract from tomato waste, obtaining blended vegetable oil.

In the second stage, the pectin is hydrated in water, in a ratio of 1:5, for 30 min, until a homogeneous gelatinous suspension is obtained.

In the third stage, in a small part of the amount of blended vegetable oil (10 g) for dressing add apple puree, gelatinous suspension of pectin, water, sugar, salt and spices.

In the Food Technology Laboratory of IP ISPHTA were prepared laboratory samples of salad dressing, which was diversified by using the addition of fat-soluble CO₂-extract from tomato waste as a source of bioactive substances.

Pic. 5. Samples of salad dressings with addition of fat-soluble CO₂- extract from tomato waste

The ingredients are mixed for about 5-10 minutes in order to obtain a stable emulsion.

In the fourth stage, vinegar is added and mixed.

In the fifth stage, the major amount of blended vegetable oil (25 g) remaining is added and mixed in a mixer with a shearing action.

The described technology allows the manufacture of a salad dressings with the advantage of obtaining a stable emulsion and in which an insignificant syneresis is possible.

The organoleptic characteristic of salad dressings is specified in table 6.

Table 6.

The organoleptic characteristic of salad dressings

Organoleptic parameter	Salad dressings	Salad dressings with addition of fat-soluble CO ₂ - extract from tomato waste
External appearance and consistency	Homogeneous mass, without agglomerations of ingredients used, creamy consistency. The presence of finely chopped parts of the ingredients used is allowed.	
Flavor and taste	Characteristic of the product, weakly sour, without foreign taste and flavor	Characteristic of the product, weakly sour, without foreign taste and flavor, with flavor of tomato and spices
Color	White with a pearly tinge, uniform throughout the mass or with inclusions of spices.	Pale orange to red-orange, due to the CO ₂ -extract of tomato, uniform throughout the mass or with inclusions of spices.

The salad dressing samples without and with the addition of fat-soluble CO₂- extract from tomato waste were tasted in the Food Technology laboratory.

Samples presented at the tasting:

1. Salad dressings with apple vinegar – control sample;
2. Salad dressings with apple vinegar and fat-soluble CO₂- extract from tomato waste;
3. Salad dressings with grape vinegar – control sample;
4. Salad dressings with grape vinegar and fat-soluble CO₂- extract from tomato waste;

5. Salad dressings with balsamic vinegar – control sample;
6. Salad dressings with balsamic vinegar and fat-soluble CO₂- extract from tomato waste;
7. Salad dressings with apple acidifier – control sample;
8. Salad dressings with apple acidifier and fat-soluble CO₂- extract from tomato waste;
9. Salad dressings with grape acidifier – control sample;
10. Salad dressings with grape acidifier and fat-soluble CO₂- extract from tomato waste.

Pic. 6. The overall average score for salad dressing samples without and with the addition of fat-soluble CO₂- extract from tomato waste

According to the score obtained, all samples of salad dressings were highly appreciated, with grades from 4.70 to 4.80. Characteristic for the tasted samples is the fact that the salad dressings with the addition of fat-soluble CO₂-extract from tomato waste were scored higher than the control samples without lipophilic addition. The evaluation of the organoleptic characteristics of the salad dressing samples is illustrated in pictures 7.1-7.3.

Pic. 7.1 Salad dressings with (a) apple vinegar and (b) grape vinegar, without and with the addition of fat-soluble CO₂- extract from tomato waste

Pic. 7.2 Salad dressings with balsamic vinegar without and with the addition of fat-soluble CO₂- extract from tomato waste

Pic. 7.3 Salad dressings with (a) apple acidifier and (b) grape acidifier, without and with the addition of fat-soluble CO₂- extract from tomato waste

Compared to the control samples, the introduction of fat-soluble CO₂- extract from tomato waste, which replaces a part of the sunflower vegetable oil, influences the organoleptic characteristics of the dressings: external appearance, color and taste. The CO₂-extract from tomato waste improves the external appearance of the products, so the samples with added lipophilic extract are more pleasant and tasty.

The physico-chemical parameters of the salad dressings with and without the addition of CO₂-extract from tomato waste were determined, the data being specified in table 7.

Table 7.

The physicochemical parameters of salad dressings with and without added CO₂-extract from tomato waste were determined

Nr. d/o	The name of product	Soluble dry substances, %		pH	Titrable acids, %		Lycopene content, mg/100 g
		without CO ₂ -extract	with CO ₂ -extract	without CO ₂ -extract	acetic acid	malic acid	with CO ₂ -extract
1	Salad dressings with apple vinegar	18,0	19,4	3,28	0,35	0,37	0,81
2	Salad dressings with grape vinegar	18,0	19,4	3,30	0,30	-	0,79
3	Salad dressings with balsamic vinegar	20,0	21,8	3,20	0,31	-	0,76
4	Salad dressings with apple acidifier	18,0	19,6	3,10	0,23	0,25	0,75
5	Salad dressings with grape acidifier	17,5	19,0	3,05	0,35	-	0,80

The physicochemical parameters were analyzed in salad dressing samples: content of soluble dry substances, content of titratable acids, pH and lycopene content.

The content of soluble dry substances for the salad dressings without CO₂-extract varies from 17.5 to 20.0%, and for those with the addition of CO₂-extract from tomato waste, it is from 19.0 to 21.8%, the maximum values being identified in salad dressings with the addition of balsamic vinegar.

The pH value is included in the range 3.05 (dressing with the addition of grape acidifier) - 3.30 (dressing with the addition of grape vinegar).

The content of titratable acids, expressed in acetic acid, is within the limits of 0.23% (dressing with added apple acidifier) and 0.35% (dressing with added apple vinegar; dressing with added grape acidifier).

The lycopene content in the dressing samples with the addition of CO₂-extract from tomato waste is 0.75

- 0.81 mg/100 g, which represents 15% of the recommended daily dose of lycopene.

Thus, as a result of the research, a food product with an increased content of biologically active components was developed - dressing with the addition of CO₂-extract from tomato waste with a lycopene content of 0.8 mg/100 g, which represents 15% of the recommended daily dose of lycopene.

Conclusions

1. Samples of fat-soluble CO₂-extracts from tomato waste were obtained in laboratory conditions.

2. The recipes of salad dressings with the addition of fat-soluble CO₂-extract from tomato waste with lycopene content in mg/100 g, which represents 15% of the recommended daily dose of lycopene, were developed.

3. Samples of salad dressings with the addition of fat-soluble CO₂-extract from tomato waste, based on apple puree, and as acidifier were used apple vinegar,

grape vinegar, balsamic vinegar, apple acidifier, grape acidifier with increased content of biologically active components, were prepared in laboratory conditions.

4. According to the organoleptic estimates, the most successful sample was the salad dressing with grape acidifier and the addition of fat-soluble CO₂-extract from tomato waste.

5. The physicochemical parameters in the samples of salad dressings: content of soluble dry substances, content of titratable acids, pH and lycopene content were determined.

References:

1. U.S. 4423084. Process for preparing salad dressings. Trainor et al. 1983.12.27.
2. Government Decision No. 196 of 25.03.2011 Health regulation regarding nutritional and health claims on food products.

3. Government Decision No. 538 of 02.09.2009 Health regulation regarding food supplements, point 15.

4. Methodical Recommendations "Rational Food" MR 2.3.1.19150-04

5. Scientific Opinion on the substantiation of health claims related to lycopene and protection of DNA, proteins and lipids from oxidative damage, protection of the skin from UV-induced (including photo-oxidative) damage, contribution to normal cardiac function (ID 1610, 2372), and maintenance of normal vision pursuant to Article 13(1) of Regulation (EC) No 1924/2006, EFSA Panel on Dietetic Products, Nutrition and Allergies (NDA), European Food Safety Authority (EFSA), Parma, Italy In: EFSA Journal, 2011, vol 9, no 4, 28 p.